

MODERN ENDODONTICS: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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In recent years, there has been a separation and development of independent sections of dentistry. There has been a clear trend towards separating endodontics into an independent section - a major subsection of dentistry, which has its own formed goals and objectives. In practical dentistry, endodontic treatment, used in the treatment of complicated forms of caries (pulpitis, periodontitis), is one of the most difficult types of treatment.

The urgency of the problem is due to the fact that the number of patients with complicated forms of caries, especially among young people, is increasing every year. Important points for the success of endodontic treatment are knowledge of the anatomical and topographic features of the structure of the tooth cavity and the root canal system, compliance with the rules of drug and instrumental treatment of the root canal, the correct choice of filling material for filling the canal, and dynamic observation using modern visual examination methods. It is necessary to develop an algorithm for the prevention of complications at the stages of endodontic treatment.

Key words: quality, endodontic, prevention, caries complications, root canal.

СОВРЕМЕННАЯ ЭНДОДОНТИЯ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПУТИ РЕШЕНИЯ

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В последние годы отмечается выделение и развитие самостоятельных разделов стоматологии. Совершенно чётко наметилась тенденция к выделению в самостоятельный раздел эндодонтии — крупного подраздела стоматологии, имеющего свои сформированные цели и задачи. В практической стоматологии эндодонтическое лечение, используемое при лечении осложнённых форм кариеса (пульпит, периодонтит), относится к наиболее сложному виду лечения. Актуальность проблемы обусловлена тем, что число пациентов с осложненными формами кариеса, особенно среди лиц молодого возраста, с каждым годом увеличивается. Важными моментами успешности эндодонтического лечения являются знание анатомо-топографических особенностей строения полости зуба и системы корневых каналов, соблюдение правил медикаментозной и инструментальной обработки корневого канала, правильный выбор пломбировочного материала для заполнения канала и динамическое наблюдение с использованием современных визуальных методов обследования. Необходима разработка алгоритма профилактики осложнений на этапах эндодонтического лечения.

Ключевые слова: качество, эндодонтия, профилактика, осложнения кариеса, корневой канал.

Build a toothache are considered the most important as long as the correct diagnosis is effective and the effectiveness of the dentist is treated. An emergency condition in endodontic refers to cases of acute toothache, edema caused by various stages of inflammation, an infectious process in the pulp or in the periodical tissue. The causes of toothache, as a rule, are caries, trauma, and damaged restoration. The term endodontic

means "endo" - inside, "donto" - tooth. That is, it is a complex of tissues located inside the tooth and including pulp and dentin, which are interconnected morphologically and functionally. These tissues develop from the dental papilla and are inextricably linked.

The pulp and dentin are connected through the processes of odontoblasts, which fill the dentinal tubules and penetrate the entire depth of the dentin. The "pulp-dentin" complex is also called the morpho-functional complex of the endodontic. In addition to dentin, the pulp of the tooth is connected with the periodontium through a neurovascular bundle that surrounds the tooth and ensures its tropism and fixation in the alveolus. Changes in the pulp lead to changes in the periodontium. Endodontics is a science that studies the structure and functions of the pulp and tissues surrounding the tooth root (periodontium), as well as a set of measures aimed at treating and preventing apical periodontitis [17]. Working with root canals always requires a highly qualified specialist, jewelry precision and care.

Endodontic is a field of dentistry that studies the structure and functions of the endodontist, the methodology and technique of manipulations in the oral cavity in case of trauma, pathological changes in the pulp, periodontium, and various other indications. Inside the tooth there is a cavity in which the coronal and root parts are distinguished. The second is also called a root canal. Its part, which goes into the coronal cavity, is the mouth of the root canal. The opening through which the tooth cavity communicates with the periodontium is called the apical apical foramen.

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Pic 1. Micrographs of the apical foramen

The micrograph of the apical openings of the root canal of the tooth (Pic. 1) clearly shows that the tooth cavity communicates with the periodontium through the main root canal and additional ones, which, in turn, often open in the region of the root apex, or in the middle third of the root, as well as in bifurcation areas (in molars). Endodontics is a high-tech industry that combines biology, medicine, physics, chemistry, pharmacology and microbiology. The ability to use technology and apply knowledge, to operate scientific research and study new trends, to question marketing theories and to follow medicine and biology are the most important qualities of a modern endodontist practitioner. Treatment of diseases of the pulp, periodontium and endodontic preparation of teeth to restore their structure and function are the most important part of practical dentistry.

Speaking about the apical foramen, it is necessary to distinguish between the anatomical apex, radiological and physiological: - the anatomical apex is the place where the root canal actually exits on the root surface; - X-ray - this is the apex of the root, which we see on the radiograph; - the physiological apex is the place of the histological transition of the pulp tissues into the periodontium. It is characterized by a narrowing of the root canal in this area. There is also a dentin-cement border here. The distance between the anatomical and physiological apex is from 0.5 to 3 mm.

Pic 2. The topography of the mouths of the root canals

On pic. 2 shows the topography of the mouths of the root canals. Many problems that arise during endodontic treatment are associated with insufficient knowledge of the anatomical and morphological features of root canals. It is important to note that, in addition to the main root canals, there are additional ones - lateral ones. They are very common, in about 50% of cases, and can be found in any part of the root, in different groups of teeth and at different canal levels. But most often they are found in the apical third of the root - just in the part where it is especially difficult to perform all endodontic manipulations. For the first time, additional channels were identified in 1970. At the same time, it was noted that in 70–90% of the flows of substances entering the pulp, they pass through the lateral channels. They usually branch off at an angle and may terminate blindly or communicate with the periodontium. There are many classifications of root canals. One of the most common is the Weine classification (Fig. 3).

Pic.3 Classification

It includes four types of root canals:

Type I - one root canal without branches;

Type II - two root canals that converge at the apex;

Type III - two parallel root canals;

Type IV - one root canal, branching into two in the lower third of the root canal. Types II and IV are the most difficult to treat. Before starting work in the root canal of the tooth, it is necessary to determine its working length. The working length of the tooth is the distance from the physiological apex to any landmark on the crown of the tooth (preserved tubercle of molars, premolars, canines, or the cutting edge of the incisors). The working length of the tooth is usually less than the radiographic length by 1–1.5 mm. It is believed that between the physiological and anatomical opening there is pulpoperiodontal tissue, which has reparative abilities. Its cells, cementoblasts and odontoblasts, are capable of producing cement and dentin, forming a biological filling, a barrier that prevents the spread of infection. Treatment of pulp and periodontal diseases and endodontic preparation of teeth to restore their structure and function are an essential part of practical dentistry.

Prevention of complications after endodontic treatment is of particular relevance due to the increase in the number of patients with complicated forms of caries, the difficulties in performing a number of medical manipulations, possible errors and complications during and after endodontic treatment. One of the causes of inflammation of the pulp and apical periodontium is dental caries. The epidemiological aspects of endodontics, compared with the epidemiology of caries and periodontal tissue diseases, have not been studied enough [6,10,14]. Studies by a number of authors have shown that 79.4% of patients had destructive changes at the root apex, resulting in poor-quality obturation of the root canal. The intensity of complicated caries per each examined averaged 3.17 teeth. High-quality obturation of root canals took place in only 40.4% of cases. The need for retreatment of root canals of teeth is almost 2.5 times higher than the need for their primary treatment

Untreated or poorly treated dental foci of infection are the cause of tooth extraction, the development of odontogenic sinusitis, chronic sepsis, which lead to temporary disability; inflammatory processes in the maxillofacial region, which sometimes cause death. One of the main problems in endodontic practice is the complexity of the topography of root canals, the so-called "problem canals". In clinical practice, a dentist often encounters situations when, after treating a tooth for pulpitis, its sensitivity to temperature stimuli remains. Patients complain of spontaneous pain or pain when biting on the tooth, which may continue for a considerable time after endodontic treatment. Dentists often explain such symptoms as a reaction to canal filling, which may be an individual sensitivity to the components of the filling material. Quite often there are clinical cases when the pulp remains in the additional root canal or the remains of the pulp in the already sealed root canal. Poor removal of the pulp from the additional root canal and its obturation is a consequence of the lack of timely diagnosis of the tooth structure and incomplete opening of its cavity.

The most problematic are the first molars of the upper jaw (medial buccal root), the incisors of the lower jaw, where additional canals are recorded. It has been established that very complex types of root canal structure do not allow to fully clean and qualitatively process the entire surface of the root canal walls. During the formation of channels, some areas remain undertreated, which negatively affects the quality of endodontic treatment. It has also been found that almost 50% of the root canal dentin wall surface can remain out of contact with endodontic instruments. The presence in the root canal system of lateral branches (93% of teeth) and branches of the apical delta (96% of teeth), which are located in the lower third of the root; in molars, additional tubules are determined in the area of bifurcation, which casts doubt on the possibility of a thorough removal of pulp tissues. The following errors are distinguished due to the complex anatomy of the root canals: in 40% the lower incisors have two root canals, in 58% the second premolar of the upper jaw has two root canals, in 31% the first premolar of the lower jaw has two root canals, in 20% the anterior teeth have lateral branches from the main root canal. Another important problem is the presence of microorganisms in the root system. Microorganisms that cause endodontic diseases and consist of 90% obligate anaerobes infect not only the soft tissues of the pulp, but also the parietal predentin of the root canal to a depth of 1.2 mm. According to statistics, the main reason for the ineffectiveness of endodontic treatment is insufficient destruction of bacteria in the root canal system (76%), incorrect determination of indications for treatment (22%), and refusal to perform radiography. Removal of pathogenic microflora from the endodontium is an etiological vector that determines the clinical course of the disease treatment and treatment plan. Root canal disinfection is essential for the regeneration of periradicular tissues. One of the necessary conditions is a thorough study of the state of the periodical tissues in the entire oral cavity. Lack of response to a temperature stimulus, tooth immobility usually indicates endodontopathology, which requires therapy. Proper endodontic treatment of the canal can eliminate periodontal pathologies of endodontic etiology, even if they have developed over a long time.

Endodontic errors associated with insufficient instrumentation, removal of microbial infection or obscuration of root canals are often caused by negligence of the doctor, misunderstanding of the concept of treatment, ignorance of the anatomy of root canals. The root of the tooth is not accessible to visual control, the channels are different in their anatomical structure, quite often there are individual features of their structure. This is the reason for the difficulties of their processing and filling. Another very important issue is the quality of canal filling, which determines the success of endodontic treatment. Studies have shown that errors in endodontic treatment, i.e. poor-quality filling of the root canal, in the analyzed material there was an incomplete filling of the canal, when the root filling occupied $\frac{2}{3}$ or $\frac{1}{2}$ of the canal. The root filling should tightly fill the canal and be located at the level of the physiological root apex, at a distance of 1-1.5 mm from the anatomical one. In 23% of observations, the filling material covered only the walls of the canal, leaving the central and apical parts of the canal empty; in some teeth, the filling mass covered only the mouth part of the canal; in 19%, the root filling at different levels of the canal was interrupted; in 15% of cases, there was excessive removal of the material beyond the apical foramen, while the root canal was obturated poorly. Currently, it is generally recognized that the removal of the filling material beyond the apex, even in destructive forms of periodontal disease, is impractical [13]. It is not uncommon for teeth with unfilled or filled canals to have pathological changes in the root apex with minimal or extensive radiological manifestations.

The final success or failure in endodontic treatment must necessarily be assessed using radiological control. One of the important points in the prevention of complications in endodontic treatment is the organ-preserving function of the tooth and the prevention of the development of odontogenic inflammatory processes in the maxillofacial region. One of the fundamental conditions for the effectiveness of endodontic conservative intervention is knowledge and understanding of the anatomy of the root canal system.

Conclusion. The given literature data indicate that the prognosis of endodontic treatment is influenced by intra- and extra-root factors. Thus, the analysis of literature data indicates the relevance of endodontic treatment at all its stages. Important points for the success of endodontic treatment are knowledge of the anatomical and topographic features of the structure of the tooth cavity and the root canal system, compliance with the rules of drug and instrumental treatment of the root canal, the correct choice of filling material for filling the canal, and dynamic observation using modern visual examination methods. The existing problems during endodontic treatment require the development of an algorithm for the prevention of complications at the stages of endodontic treatment. The results of our observations indicate the prospects of studying this problem by conducting a clinical and statistical analysis of medical records to identify the causes that contribute to various complications, and the need to develop an algorithm for preventing complications.

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